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Responses of Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* Moench) to Low Levels of Cadmium Compared to Ascorbic Acid, Biomin and Potassium Sulfate

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted in 2019 in pots to study the response of okra seedlings (two weeks old) to low cadmium chloride concentration (0.001 and 0.0001 ppm), compared to ascorbic acid (50 and 100 ppm), biomin (3 and 6 ppm) and potassium sulfate (50 ppm) as well as control. Complete randomized design with four replicates was used. Fresh and dry weight of shoots and roots as well as chlorophyll was determined. The results showed that all treatments had no significant differences compared to control, but all treatments except potassium sulfate caused significant increase in root length compared to control treatment. Biomin at 6 ppm caused a significant increase of plant fresh weight whereas at 3 and 6 ppm caused a significant increase of plant dry weight. Biomin and potassium sulfate caused a significant increase of chlorophyll.

Keywords: Ascorbic acid; Biomin; Cadmium chloride; Potassium sulfate; Okra

Introduction

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* Moench) is a summer vegetable plant grown in all tropical regions as well as the warmer parts of subtropical regions. Heavy metal toxicity is one of the major abiotic stress which leads to hazardous effects in plants. Heavy metals had high reactivity that directly influences growth, senescence and energy synthesis processes. It inhibits the growth processes or decrease the activity of photosynthetic apparatus often correlated with progression of senescence processes (Sharma and Agrawal, 2010; Duquesnay et al., 2010) as well as shortened and thickened or poorly developed roots (Khudsar et al., 2004). Cadmium (Cd) is a highly phytotoxic at low concentrations (Yang et al., 2004). Cadmium being a highly toxic metal pollutant of soils, inhibits root and shoot growth and then plant yield. The induced inhibition extent on plant growth, photosynthesis, water uptake, and nutrients assimilation is greatly dependent on the metal ions concentration, and the plant thresholds of toxicity characteristic. Al Riyahi (2011) found that low levels of cadmium (0.001 and 0.0001 ppm) can stimulate roots branching and significantly increased roots number compared to the control.

Ascorbic acid has important role as a cofactor of a large number of key enzymes (Arrigoni and de Tullio, 2000). Biomin is a natural organic fertilizer derived from hydrolyzed vegetable proteins to supply nitrogen to plants which stabilize the soil organic matter and contains chelated plant nutrients. Mohammed et al. (2018) showed that spray biomin as foliar application to chili pepper gives higher values for leaf area, leaf number, chlorophyll index as well as root and shoot biomass. Potassium plays important regulatory roles in the plant, i.e., regulation of plant stomata and water use, translocation of sugars and carbohydrates formation, enzyme regulation activities, protein synthesis and many other processes needed to sustain plant growth and development (Hsiao and Läuchli, 1986).

Materials and methods

The seeds of okra were soaked for 12 hours at night and then sown in plastic pots containing sandy loamy soil washed three times to remove the salts and metals. Three uniformed seedlings were sustained after germination in each pot. The experimental design was completely randomized design with 8 treatments and 4 replicates. After 2 weeks from germination the seedlings were treated with cadmium chloride (0.001 and 0.0001 ppm), ascorbic acid (50 and 100 ppm), biomin (3 and 6 ppm), K_2SO_4 (50 ppm) as well as distil water (control treatment). After 14 days chlorophyll ratio in leaves were conducted by chlorophyll meter and the seedlings were taken carefully to determine its fresh weight and the length of root and shoot. Then the fresh samples were dried in oven (70 C°) for 48 h to determine the dry weights.

Results and discussion

Table 1 showed that foliar application of cadmium chloride at low concentration (0.0001 and 0.001ppm) stimulates root length compared to control treatment with an increase percentage of 38% and 31.8% respectively. This result was agreed with Hameed et al. (2011) who revealed that root length showed an enhancement with 0.05 mM $CdCl_2$ and then decline with increasing the concentrations. The positive effect on plant growth by low cadmium levels has been poorly discussed in literature but two possible mechanisms can be suggested. According to Kennedy and Gonsalves (1987) low cadmium levels hyperpolarize the plasma membrane at the root surface thus increasing the trans-membrane potential, which is an energy source for cation uptake. Moreover cadmium has been found to induce gene related to mammalian cell proliferation which could increase growth, though they are also considered responsible for cadmium induced carcinogenesis (Beyersmann,2002). The results indicate that okra is tolerant to high concentrations of this metal, due to a different activation of its enzymatic antioxidant system.

Ascorbic acid at both concentrations (50 and 100 ppm) caused a significant increase in root length compared to control with a percentage increase of 27.2% and 18.6% respectively. This result may be due to the role of ascorbic acid as a redox buffer and as a cofactor for enzymes involved in regulating photosynthesis, hormone biosynthesis, regenerating other antioxidants and regulates cell division and growth. The result was in line with Farooq et al. (2013). It is also in line with Athar et al. (2008) who mentioned that endogenous AsA levels can be improved by exogenous supply of AsA via foliar spry.

Table 1: Effect of $CdNO_3$, AsA, Biomin and K_2SO_4 on Okra seedlings

Treatment	Stem length	Root length	Fresh weight	Dry weight	Chlorophyll
Control	10.67	43.00	2.57	0.397	25.87
0.0001 $CdNO_3$ ppm	10.67	59.33	2.23	0.370	29.73
0.001 $CdNO_3$ ppm	10.00	56.67	2.07	0.323	26.93
50 AsA ppm	10.33	54.70	2.63	0.380	28.07
100 AsA ppm	10.00	51.00	2.57	0.370	26.50
Biomin 3 ppm	11.67	53.00	3.10	0.460	30.37
Biomin 6 ppm	12.00	59.67	3.70	0.580	31.57
K_2SO_4 50 ppm	11.33	49.33	3.03	0.373	30.73
LSD _{0.05}	1.58	7.88	0.51	0.030	3.91

Biomin application at 3 and 6 ppm caused a significant increase in stem length, root length, fresh and dry weight and chlorophyll index compared to control treatment, with an increase percentage of 9.4, 23.3, 20.6, 15.9, 17.4 and 12.5, 38.8, 44, 46.1, 22 respectively and this results due to biomin composition of hydrolyzed vegetable proteins that supply nitrogen to plants

which is important for living cells, enzymes, proteins and photosynthesis and that will aid plant growth and improves leaf quality. This result was agreed with Fahimi et al. (2016).

Potassium sulfate K_2SO_4 (50 ppm) caused slightly effect on chlorophyll index with an increase percentage of 18.8%. This result was agreed with Tuna et al. (2010) who showed that additional supply of K enhancing chlorophyll content. This increase may belong to potassium role on chlorophyll genesis catalyst hormones in leaf like cytokinine which is necessary to originate the chloroplast during leaf growth and development.

Conclusion

It could be concluded that low cadmium concentration stimulates okra root growth significantly compared to control. Biomin caused a significant increase in fresh and dry weight as well as chlorophyll content. Potassium causes a significant increase in chlorophyll content.

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Author Contributions

IAA and AHJ conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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Competing interest

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Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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